

Design of growth-coupled measurements of single-chain antibody fragment function

A proposal for onboarding Single-Chain Antibody Fragments to the protein sequence-to-function measurement platform.

- Uses a gene circuit to tie Single-Chain Antibody Fragment activity to bacterial cell growth
- Calibration variants span the dynamic range of activity enable quantitative function measurements
- First dataset collection will focus on anti-IL-6 Single-Chain Antibody Fragments.

Overview

We are building a new class of optical biosensors comprised of quantum defect-functionalized carbon nanotubes conjugated to designed single-chain antibody fragments (scFvs) fashioned to make implantable nanosensors that detect proinflammatory cytokines such as human Interleukin-6 (hIL-6) in patients in real time. hIL-6 is a clinical biomarker for a number of important diseases, including ovarian cancer, lung cancer, and cytokine storm in sepsis, covid, and Car-T syndrome in patients undergoing cancer immunotherapy. Our first paper on this was recently published in JACS¹. Increased affinity to the cytokine target will improve

sensitivity and expand dynamic range in our sensor platform. In addition to hIL-6, we intend to expand on this approach to target several additional cytokines, eventually enabling the design of high-affinity scFvs to cytokine targets outside of our dataset. With Align to Innovate we will create datasets that will enable the development of new AI approaches to predictively engineer scFvs and other loop-presenting proteins as sensing elements for a diverse set of cytokines relevant to human health.

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Significance and Impact

The target. Antibodies, formed by hypervariable CDR loop selection to make high affinity recognition surfaces in acquired immunity, are central to the immune systems of mammals. Their biological superpower is the high-affinity, high-selectivity binding of target proteins, or antigens. As such, they play a starring role in many clinical tests and biosensors. Expressed versions of these proteins, termed ‘monoclonal antibodies’, are created by injecting antigens into an animal – typically a rabbit or dog – and then days later the B-cells that present antibodies that bind the antigen are captured and the antibodies sequenced. Besides the animal sacrifice involved in monoclonal antibody creation, there are some other non-idealities in this method: the binding surface cannot be specified, the specific antigen conformation may not be able to be targeted, the antigen cannot be overly toxic (meaning it is difficult to create monoclonals to bioweapons), the antigen might not provoke a large enough immune response, and the process locks the protein into the unstable and difficult-to-work-with immunoglobulin fold. The ability to computationally create antibodies and antibody-like proteins quickly would circumvent all of these problems, leading to more effective biosensors and clinical antibodies. While computational design often focuses on creating the tightest possible binding, information about mutations that alter binding affinity in non-optimized sequences will provide information often lacking in published datasets. Many databases of protein interactions already exist,³⁻⁶ some of which exclusively focus on antibody-antigen interactions.⁷⁻⁹ And while these provide a great deal of information, for a single protein-protein interaction these datasets contain either a large number of variants without binding affinities, or much smaller number of variants with measured affinities. The capability to select the analyte binding affinity of a designed protein is critical for the development of biosensors, in which the binding affinity must be matched to the dynamic range of the analyte as opposed to being merely as tight as possible. Furthermore this knowledge will enable adjustments when external design constraints impose non-favorable mutations, such as with the removal of disulfide linkages in our single-chain scFvs.

We are creating a biosensor for interleukin-6 (IL-6), a proinflammatory cytokine secreted by macrophages. Elevated levels of IL-6 are associated with a variety of pathological disease conditions including rheumatoid arthritis, cytokine release syndrome, and Castleman’s disease.¹⁰ As a biomarker, IL-6 levels are increased in patients with a variety of autoimmune diseases, metabolic diseases, cancers and infections. We currently have CDMRP funding to create an implantable ovarian cancer detector centered on IL-6 quantification. Additionally, our collaborators at Sloan-Kettering are very interested in creating real-time biosensors for cytokine release syndrome (CRS), or cytokine storm using a microneedle patch format. This is because CRS is a common cause of fatal outcomes in cancer immunotherapies – a disease called Chimeric antigen receptor T cell (CART) syndrome.¹¹ Real-time sensing of systemic inflammation will enable medical intervention before CRS develops, a first in CRS management.

Our single-chain variety fragment sequence is derived from a published hIL-6 binding monoclonal antibody structure¹² with two internal disulfide bonds removed to enable a full folding transition upon ligand binding, enhancing the electric field change concomitant to binding and thus improving sensitivity.¹ Currently, our scFv designs bind to IL-6 with an affinity of approximately 500 nM, with a lower limit of detection of 30 nM. Slightly higher sensitivity is needed for detection in patient sera, as interstitial IL-6 levels can range from 10 nM in healthy patients to >400 nM in patients undergoing CRS.¹ Thus optimization of this interaction to create sensors that cover this dynamic range is necessary next step in our nanosensor development. While IL-6 is the cytokine most correlated with fatal outcomes in CRS, there are several other structurally related cytokines, including IL-1 β , IL-10, and IL-21, that serve as inflammatory biomarkers for CRS and other diseases.

Other anti-cytokine datasets. scFvs are favorite targets of phage-display library selection. As such, there are many examples of end-product sequences of several rounds of ‘biopanning’ for improved affinity.¹³⁻¹⁵ However, these are typically limited to a few high-affinity binders that ‘win’ the selection competition. There are two issues which limit these approaches: (i) this kind of limited sequence search does not result in the highest possible affinity, as successive rounds of selection go down a single local minima in sequence space without exploring the full landscape, and (ii) paradoxically, only searching for the tightest possible binders limits the possible utility of the binding event, as in many cases reversible binding is desired and in the case of very high affinity binders dissociation rates can be hours or even days.^{16, 17}

Dataset generation. We will construct a dataset comprised of anti IL-6 scFv sequences correlated with their inferred binding affinities. Our plan is to use split dihydrofolate reductase (DHFR) complementation¹⁸⁻²¹ as a growth-based strategy to optimize anti-IL-6 scFv binding to its target cytokine. Briefly, a barcoded library of anti-IL-6 scFv variants will be attached to one half of the mouse version of DHFR (an essential metabolic enzyme), and the target IL-6 cytokine will be attached to the other (Figure 1). Both proteins will be expressed from a single plasmid in the Marrionette *E. coli* strain developed to enable expression of multiple proteins using low-background, high dynamic range expression control via orthogonal small molecule inducers.⁸ Successful association of the scFv with the cytokine will drive DHFR assembly, and tighter binding results in faster growth. There are three primary ‘knobs’ available to select for a particular binding affinity: (i) Trimethoprim will be added to inhibit the bacterial DHFR, and increased levels of the inhibitor increases selective pressure, (ii,iii) the relative and absolute levels of the two proteins can be manipulated using different concentrations of the small molecule inducers.

For the library measurement, we will use a protocol similar to the pooled, growth-based assays²² developed for other Align to Innovate sequence-function datasets. Briefly, we will use an automated bacterial growth and measurement platform to grow

Figure 1: Alphafold model of the split DHFR:IL6 pairing. The two halves of the DHFR are in yellow and green, and the attached scFv and cytokine are in purple and red, respectively

each transformed library in 24 different conditions (different concentrations of trimethoprim and the small molecule inducers)²³. The 24 conditions will allow us to measure full binding isotherms by inducing each half of the split DHFR system individually. This will allow us to quantitatively measure growth rates corresponding to binding affinities spanning a wide range. As with other Align growth-based assays²², we will repeatedly dilute and grow the bacterial cells over four time points, keeping the cell density at or below mid-log phase to simplify quantitative data analysis. At the end of each time point, we will extract plasmid DNA²⁴ from each sample and use next-gen sequencing (Illumina NovaSeq) to quantify the relative abundance of each barcoded scFv variant²⁵. We will use two types of spike-in controls to convert sequencing read counts to quantitative estimates of fitness in each condition and then to binding affinity. The first type of spike in will be a normalization control, which will have constitutive expression of an intact mouse DHFR and a distinct barcode; we will normalize the read counts for each barcoded scFv variant by the spike-in barcode count to give a quantitative fitness value for each scFv variant in each sample. Then, we will use a set of calibration spike-in variants (scFvs with known binding affinity) to quantitatively calibrate from fitness to binding affinity. We will use the Singleplex function assay (microscale thermophoresis, see below) to measure the affinities of the spike-in ScFvs to create the necessary (non-linear) calibration curve.

The plasmid for this dataset project will be based on the split-DHFR protein complementation assay (PCA, Fig. 1). Murine DHFR is split into two fragments (DHFR1,2 and DHFR3), each expressed as a fusion protein with a flexible linker and either the single-chain variable fragment (scFv) or the binding target (e.g., Interleukin-6, IL-6). The expression of the split-DHFR proteins in the presence of trimethoprim provides the selection for the fitness assays. Trimethoprim inhibits the activity of bacterial DHFR. Without a functional DHFR gene, bacteria cannot replicate. When the two genes of interest (IL-6 and scFv) interact, they bring the two DHFR fragments together to reform a functional murine DHFR protein, which is not inhibited by trimethoprim, allowing the bacteria to continue replication. In this way, the binding affinity between our genes of interest is directly tied to the rate of bacterial replication.

The two DHFR fragment fusions will be expressed from independently inducible expression cassettes using promoters from the *E. coli* Marionette system²⁶ (with assays implemented in the Marionette-Clo *E. coli* strain). DHFR1,2 will be expressed as a fusion protein with the scFv under the control of the pVanCC inducible promoter (induced with vanillic acid). DHFR3 will be expressed as a fusion protein with the IL-6 under the control of the inducible promoter pSalTTC (induced with salicylic acid). Ribozyme insulators (PlmJ and RiboJ) and bicistronic translational control elements (BCDs) are included to increase translation efficiency and to minimize changes

in gene expression due to changes in the scFv sequence. With each fusion gene regulated by separate inducible promoters, the protein expression levels can be varied across different samples in the pooled growth-based assay²³ to effectively measure binding isotherms between the scFv and IL-6. Independent inducible control of each fusion gene also reduces the requirement for precise tuning of the other circuit components (promoters, BCDs) to achieve optimal protein ratios, which should make initial plasmid tuning and testing easier and faster.

Similar to other Align to Innovate growth-based assays²², the circuit shown in Fig. 2 will be implemented in the medium-copy, kanamycin-resistant Twist cloning vector (with p15A origin). We have already ordered and tested a similar plasmid in that Twist vector, with GFP and RFP in place of the DHFR-fragment fusion genes. In those test plasmids, both inducible cassettes give greater than 300-fold dynamic range (ratio of fully induced to basal expression level).

Gene of Interest (GOI) Region

The gene of interest region contains the DHFR1,2-scFv cassette. (Figure 3)

Mutations will be made to three 33-amino acid regions (Figure 4) which cover three of the complementary determining regions (CDRs) as well as important residues in the upper core or in the interface between heavy and light chains. These 33 residue regions are limited to this size due to Twist's library construction technology.

Figure 3: Scheme for the gene of interest region.

Figure 4: Mutation sites within the gene of interest. (A) Amino acid sequence of the α IL6 scFv. Residues within 5 Å of the IL-6 ligand are highlighted in red. Asterisks indicate the former position of disulfide bridges. The cysteine residues were removed to allow the phase-changing behavior of the supercharged proteins. The black lines adjacent to regions 1 (yellow), 2 (green) and 3 (cyan) show the range of potential mutation sites using Twist Bioscience's gene synthesis, while the colored backgrounds indicate which sites were actually selected for mutations. (B-C) Cartoon representation of the α IL6 scFv (grey) bound to the IL6 ligand (black). PDB ID: 4ZS7 (B) Residues within 5 Å of the IL-6 ligand are highlighted in red. (C) Residues selected for mutation are shown as spheres. The colors correspond to the highlighted regions in panel A.

Selection Cassette

The Selection Cassette is the inducible cassette that contains the Action Site, which is the target protein (e.g., IL-6).

Figure 5: Scheme for the Selection Cassette region.

Barcode Region

The plasmid for the pooled assay will include a barcode region adjacent to the GOI (to the right of the DT5 terminator in Figs. 2-3). The barcoding approach includes tagging both the backbone and insert with “half” barcodes to allow the library to be assembled with a unique barcode for each GOI variant. The plasmid for the pooled assay will have

the same barcode region used for other Align to Innovate growth-based assays, e.g., the same priming locations for PCR-amplification of the barcodes. This will facilitate reuse of the same primers and barcode sequencing library preparation protocol with minimal additional validation.

Proposed Hosts and Plasmids

Our proposed host is Marionette-Clo *E. coli* (derived from DH10B). Marionette strains have been developed to respond to different small-molecule inducers (including vanillic acid and salicylic acid) by the genomic incorporation of the transcription factors necessary to respond

to these inducers. By using this strain, we no longer require the incorporation of the transcription factors (VanR and nahR) into our designed plasmid.

Benchling:
[Link](#)

Proposed Protein Targets

Our initial target in Phase II is the human Interleukin-6, a helical bundle proinflammatory cytokine. In Phase III, once the target has been measured and a predictive model derived from the data, we intend to expand our target set to other structurally similar cytokines which are also important cancer biomarkers: IL-1 β , IL-2, IL-10, and IL-17.

Proposed Controls for Assay Development

To achieve the goals for engineering tighter-binding scFvs to IL-6, we will need a pooled assay that can measure binding affinity across a wide range, from low nanomolar to micromolar. So, for Stage 1 assay development and tuning, we will use the SARS-CoV spike protein heptad repeat, HR2, as the binding target (Action Site), and scFvs reported with different affinities for HR22. In addition, we will use IL-6 paired with an scFv with the highest affinity that is currently available.

Stage 1 - Development and Tuning

During initial plasmid development and tuning, we will test different expression levels for each expression cassette by varying the strength of the BCD components (see Fig. 2) and testing with the set of GOI and action site sequences listed in Table B1. The goal will be to choose the BCD strengths and assay conditions (trimethoprim and inducer concentrations) that provide the best measurement with the widest dynamic range for different binding affinities, ideally between 5 nM - 500 nM.

The Singleplex Function assay will be used to calibrate the pooled, growth-based assay to real biophysical units (binding constant or ΔG). In our case we will use microscale thermophoresis (MST) with bacterially expressed and HPLC-purified proteins. We have already demonstrated the use of this assay in our initial anti-IL-6 scFv development¹. The assay detects the interaction between molecules by quantifying the thermophoretic movement of fluorescent molecules in response to a temperature gradient.²⁷ Briefly, fluorescently labeled scFv is mixed with different concentrations of the nonfluorescent ligand, and a temperature gradient is applied to samples in capillaries tubes. The flow of the

fluorescent molecule in the temperature gradient is quantified and its hydrodynamic radius calculated (Figure 6). The effect of different concentrations of the nonfluorescent ligand on the hydrodynamic radius of the fluorescent molecule enables the determination of the binding affinity between the two molecules. MST has the advantage that it is rapid, requires only nanograms of sample, has a wide dynamic range, and our current device enables the quantification of up to five binding affinities in one hour-long run.

In phase I, we will confirm the binding affinities of all four protein pairs using MST. To determine the additional binding energy, if any, imparted by the addition of the DHFR fragments on the protein association we will likewise determine the affinity of these proteins with their DHFR fragments attached and compare affinities with those of the free binding pair. In later phases a selected subset of binders from the pooled growth-based assay²³ with a range of apparent affinities will have their binding energies quantified using MST to further calibrate the library results.

Stage 2 - Normalization and Calibration Controls

Normalization control plasmids will be transformed into *E. coli* cells and added to the pooled assay (i.e., spiked in).²³ They will be used to normalize the barcode counts in each sample, and thus need to have the same barcode region as the assay plasmid, and they require a relatively high fitness in all assay conditions. To satisfy these requirements, we will use a plasmid design with the same barcode region as the assay plasmid, but with only a single gene expression cassette for constitutive expression of intact mDHFR at a sufficient level to completely restore normal growth in the presence of trimethoprim.

Calibration control plasmids will also be added as spike-ins to the pooled assay²³. The scFv-target pairs used in the calibration plasmids will be measured using the singleplex function assay (MST), and the results will be used in combination with the pooled fitness results²³ to calibrate from the measured fitness values to the protein function values (binding). For calibration controls, we will use the scFv-target pairs listed in Table 1, plus a selection of 8-16 additional scFv-target chosen to span the full range of binding affinity for the measurement. We will select those additional scFv-target pairs from existing data, e.g., the same HR2 binding dataset that we used to identify the GOI sequences listed in Table 1.

Figure 6: hIL-6 binding to our scFv quantified using microscale thermophoresis (MST). (Top) Raw thermophoretic mobility data. Decreasing mobility with increasing ligand concentration indicated with an arrow. (Bottom) Replot of scFv mobility as a function of hIL-6 concentration. Line drawn is a fit with the tight binding equation with a K_d of 490 nM.

Action site sequences	GOI sequences	Expected activity
HR2	AAYL50_983	High
HR2	AAYL51_7995	Low
HR2	AAYL50_19764	None
IL-6	Best available scFV	500 nM

Table 1: Initial plasmid variants to be used for circuit tuning.

Pilot-Scale Collection: IL-6

As described above, our Phase II research plan is to generate a dataset of anti-IL-6 variants with attached fitness scores that we will experimentally benchmark to binding energies. The initial pilot will be split into three mutational libraries. In the first library, mutations will be made to three 33-amino acid regions (Figure 4) which cover three of the complementary determining regions (CDRs) as well as important residues in the upper core or in the interface between heavy and light chains. These 33 residue regions are limited to this size due to Twist's library construction technology. The second library will cover all possible single amino acids changes, all deletions and

all substitutions. The third library will consist of a random multi-mutational library, created by error-prone PCR.

This will both establish a workflow to be used by us and others to create protein-protein binding datasets centered on important interactions, and enable us to create a protein language model that enables us to generate anti-IL-6 scFvs with targeted affinities. Additionally, variants that push the upper and lower limits of the dynamic range of assay at this stage will be incorporated as calibration controls to expand the assay's ability to measure a wider range of affinities in large-scale runs.

Large-Scale Collection: IL-1 β , IL-2, IL-10, and IL-17

The Phase III research plan involves using our optimized workflow to generate binding datasets for the structurally related cytokines IL-1 β , IL-2, IL-10, and IL-17. This will create a global dataset intended to lead to a protein language model that enables the creation of anti-cytokine scFvs both to these cytokines and others.

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